

Greenpeace Indonesia's Open Donation Strategy in Increasing Participation on Climate Change Issues in Timbulsloko Village

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Abstract: Why does Greenpeace open donations to the Indonesian people?. The issue of climate change has currently attracted a lot of attention worldwide, including Indonesia. The involvement of various parties is not only carried out by the government and society but also by non-governmental organizations, one of which is Greenpeace. This article will examine the phenomenon of open donations for seaside flood victims in Timbulsloko village in increasing public participation, where this village has become one of the concerns of Greenpeace Indonesia so that several efforts have been made to resolve this problem, one of which is open donations. Seeing this phenomenon, this research wants to see what made Greenpeace take the initiative to open donations to the Indonesian people. By examining the phenomenon of open donations made by Greenpeace to victims affected by the ROB flood in Timbulsloko village, Indonesia, this research argues that the efforts made by Greenpeace in opening donations are one of Greenpeace's ways of increasing community participation to be aware of the phenomenon of the impact of climate change present in real life. Using a case study method in Timbulsloko Village, this research will try to see what motivates Greenpeace to open donations in general, and what motivates the community to get involved in donations.

Keywords: *Climate Change, Greenpeace, Participation, Timbulsloko Villag.*

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I. INTRODUCTION

Why did Greenpeace start a donation campaign in Indonesia, especially for Timbulsloko Village?. Many studies try to discuss how Greenpeace Indonesia carries out actions such as campaigns and opening donations as a strategy to overcome various environmental impact problems. However, this research tries to find and show points from a different point of view, namely that the act of opening donations to the Indonesian people is considered as a strategy to increase awareness and increase community participation that the impact of climate change is real, especially in one case in Timbulsloko Village where there has been no research about that.

This Climate change has now become a global problem that touches almost all aspects of people's lives. The term climate change usually refers to long-term variations, such as changes in the average weather in a place over a certain period of time, for at least thirty years (Amstrong, AK, et al, 2018). Unfortunately, since the late 1800s, human activities have increased the amount of greenhouse gases released into the atmosphere through the burning of fossil fuels (such as oil,

gas, and coal) and to a lesser extent, through land use change and deforestation. As a result, the intensification of the greenhouse effect increases global surface temperatures and causes significant changes to the environment. Today, compared to previous times in the history of our society, these changes are occurring very quickly (East-West Center, 2021).

Global Weather Change Data released in 2023 by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) shows that the last eight years have been the hottest period on earth, with an average increase of about 1 degree Celsius since the end of the 19th century. The impact of global warming is very broad, touching all corners of the earth and impacting the lives of billions of people. The United Nations Office of Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) published a report showing that natural disasters impacted an average of 410 million people per year from 2000 to 2019, and 90% of these disasters were caused by climate change. In addition, climate change will have impacts at local and national levels on health, mortality, food security, migration patterns, natural ecosystems and economic well-being.

In Indonesia itself, the impact of climate change is very severe for Indonesia, where this country has large islands and a long coastline, resulting in unique climate change. With more than 17,000 islands and a coastline of more than 54,000 km, Indonesia is very vulnerable to the impacts of climate change because its entire identity is linked to the sea. Possible dangers to the country's ecology, economy and society are rising sea levels, frequent flooding, prolonged drought and loss of biodiversity (World Bank, 2020). Therefore, in facing increasingly serious climate problems, not only governments but non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have also become important players on the international stage, advocating for environmental protection and climate action. These organizations, which are often the combined result of grassroots organizations, scientific knowledge, and international networks, are involved in a wide range of climate change activities, from advocating for legislation and the needs of the general public to raising awareness of the issue.

Among the vanguard NGOs focused on climate change, Greenpeace is a respected and iconic force. Currently, based on profile data, Greenpeace is an international organization that campaigns to protect the earth. Its head office is located in Amsterdam, while in Indonesia it is located in Jakarta. Founded in 1971, Greenpeace now has several offices in 51 countries with supporters reaching 2.8 million. The focus of the campaign includes environmental issues, namely forestry, water, energy and marine as well as campaigning for stricter environmental regulations, promoting the use of renewable energy sources (Greenpeace Indonesia, 2020)

Greenpeace is renowned for its relentless commitment to protecting the environment and fighting climate change. The organization continually challenges the advocacy status quo to highlight the importance of a sustainable future, to combat global warming, deforestation, pollution and biodiversity loss. Greenpeace's willingness to question existing norms and take direct action is a key feature of its climate campaign. Massive protests, creative awareness-raising initiatives, and a fierce determination to hold governments and corporations accountable for their role in causing climate change are common features of these organizations' efforts. These protests have not only drawn attention to climate change around the world, but also served as a reminder of the importance of taking action (Greenpeace, 2021).

Greenpeace is also actively working in Indonesia, where they play an important role in solving the climate problems that exist in this country. Indonesia's geographic diversity, with extensive coastlines, rainforests and landscapes rich in biodiversity, makes Indonesia a focal point for Greenpeace's efforts. The organization operates locally in Indonesia, collaborating with communities and advocating for policies that mitigate the impacts of climate change and encourage sustainable practices.

Greenpeace Indonesia has taken proactive steps to address climate-related problems in the country, one of which is the problem that occurred in Timbulloko Village, which is

currently known as a sinking village. Greenpeace has started a donation campaign which in this research is assumed to be aimed at increasing awareness and providing support to communities affected by climate change, as evidenced by their response to coastal flooding in the village of Timbulloko. Understanding why Greenpeace, which has international access, chose to engage Indonesian society through donation campaigns is the main question this research seeks to explore.

The main research question guiding this research is an important investigation into the motivations and strategies that drive Greenpeace, a global environmental NGO, to actively seek donations from the Indonesian public. This question encapsulates a broader curiosity regarding the dynamics of environmental activism, community involvement, and awareness of climate change in the Indonesian context. As a country in a unique position to witness the direct impacts of climate change, the motivation behind Greenpeace's choice to engage the Indonesian people through donations is very interesting. This prompts us to explore the underlying motivations behind these strategic choices. What prompted Greenpeace to actively involve the Indonesian people in supporting issues related to climate change, and how has this campaign influenced public involvement and awareness of climate change in this archipelagic country? This research seeks to uncover the ins and outs of Greenpeace's approach to donation campaigns, with a particular focus on the village of Timbulloko, which is an example of the local challenges posed by climate change. By investigating the motivations, strategies and outcomes of Greenpeace's donation initiative in Timbulloko, this research aims to uncover the broader dynamics of climate activism.

➤ *In this Research, Researchers used Several Literatures to better Understand the Concept of this Research:*

Climate change is one of the biggest problems in the world today, impacting countries and communities everywhere, including Indonesia. To address this serious problem, several stakeholders have come together to address climate change. Various campaigns and events have been held to spread awareness of the issue of climate change, especially by organizations dedicated to the issue. Apart from the government and society, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) also play an important role in raising public awareness, encouraging policy changes, and implementing programs to reduce the impacts of climate change and adapt to it, for example Friends of the Earth and Greenpeace have been campaigning on the issue of climate change since the 1980s. Activism began in earnest in the 1990s, and more campaign groups were formed in the 2000s, working and collaborating on climate change (UK Parliament, 2022).

Currently, many climate change campaigns and movements are also carried out by the younger generation who are starting to realize that they, like Gen Z and Millennials, are often on the front lines of climate change, with voices demanding action and providing hope. Consistently, it appears that Generation Z (Gen Z) and

Millennials are more likely than older age groups, especially Generation X (Gen actively engage in initiatives aimed at addressing the critical issue of climate change. This younger generation has demonstrated a greater commitment to environmental sustainability through their active participation in various activities and campaigns, demonstrating their fight against climate change. Common activities include donating funds to organizations focused on addressing climate change, contacting elected officials to urge them to take action on climate change, volunteering for activities focused on addressing climate change, and attending protests or demonstrations to show support for climate change (Pew Research, 2021). Climate activists around the world relentlessly seek global solidarity and transformational change with a clear and urgent message: act now to tackle climate change.

One common strategy used by NGOs to address the impacts of climate change is the use of donations and fundraising campaigns. These initiatives serve as important mechanisms to provide immediate assistance and support to communities affected by climate change-related disasters (Lastri, 2014). Giving not only helps those in need financially, but also shows that the world is united in confronting climate change. They can help fund immediate relief, support community rebuilding, and add to long-term efforts to increase resilience (Rachmasari et al., 2016). Therefore, integrating society in efforts to overcome climate

change is also very necessary to increase awareness and action. Participation in local initiatives increases awareness of the real-world impacts of climate change by encouraging a sense of ownership and responsibility (Creswell & Devraj, 2019). Because the impacts of climate change are usually felt first and foremost at the environmental level, community participation is key to developing workable solutions (Ministry of Environment and Forestry, 2018).

On the other hand, the importance of finding out why society and the business world contribute to the causes of climate change cannot be ignored. Several elements, such as compassion, empathy, personal beliefs, and a desire for social change, have been identified by researchers as important elements in inspiring people to donate to environmental and humanitarian organizations. These factors are critical to the success of climate change programs, including funding and community involvement. As a well-known environmental NGO, Greenpeace has been active in the fight against climate change and relief operations after natural disasters. Greenpeace is driven by its mission to protect the environment, promote sustainable practices, and educate the public about the impacts of climate change (Greenpeace, 2023). Greenpeace's strategy in dealing with the impacts of climate change can be better understood by looking at its motivations and tactics in the Indonesian context. Below I attach the framework of this research:

Fig 1: Framework of Thinking

II. DISCUSSION

In this chapter, the researcher details the main findings obtained through this research which investigates the reasons why Greenpeace opened donations among Indonesian people and explores the motivations of Indonesian people in participating in these donations. This research is based on a concrete case related to ROB (Quantity Remaining On Board) flooding in Timbulsloko Village, which is one of Greenpeace Indonesia's main concerns. The ROB flood case in Timbulsloko Village has a different context in Greenpeace Indonesia's policy. This situation is different from other problems faced by Greenpeace in Indonesia because local communities feel the direct impact of climate change. Timbulsloko residents appear to be very concerned about ROB flooding caused by rising sea levels and coastal erosion.

Based on interviews conducted by Audhea (2023) with the people of Timbulsloko Village, it was stated that Timbulsloko village was previously a rice field area where many crops were planted, but in 2012 some of the rice fields could no longer be planted because sea levels began to rise which caused several rice fields to be converted. function as a pond. Until 2017, rising sea water caused all of the pond land to be submerged and could not be sown with seeds again. Not only ponds, residents' houses and a number of other public facilities such as places of worship were also submerged by tidal floods. According to Astra (2014), the 2000s saw the beginning of land erosion in Timbulsloko Village, and in 2013 Timbulsloko Hamlet experienced land decline of around 400-1300 meters in its coastal area. This is what has caused the shift in land function that occurred in Timbulsloko Village from agricultural land to fish ponds and until now the pond land can no longer be planted with seeds.

Fig 2: Condition of Timbulsloko

This condition resulted in various impacts felt by the community, such as the inundation of a number of residents' land (agricultural land, ponds, houses and other facilities) and changes in the community in Timbulsloko Hamlet, such as

loss of livelihood, social changes and the community's environmental conditions. The image above is one of the impacts received by the people of Dukuh Timbulsloko as a result of climate change and changes in ecosystem form. According to Harmoni (2015), climate change has a major impact on coastal ecosystems, especially sea level rise, changes in acidity and temperature and the subsequent impacts, namely inundation of agricultural land, damage to infrastructure, damage to property and diversity of biological resources. The rise of water to the surface has a very detrimental impact on the people of Timbulsloko Village in their daily lives, such as hampering people's activities and mobility. The water that entered people's houses never receded, causing damage to connecting roads between villages and various kinds of household furniture and also requiring people to raise their houses.

Greenpeace is an international environmental NGO that uses peaceful protest, creative communication, and nonviolent direct action to expose global environmental problems and promote solutions for a green and peaceful future (Marshall, 2013). As Bohlen (2021) said, Greenpeace is an international environmental non-governmental organization (NGO) that uses a non-violent "creative confrontation" strategy to demonstrate environmental violations committed by governments, industries and companies. Greenpeace has developed into the world's leading environmental campaign organization thanks to its combination of important environmental issues with peaceful efforts.

Greenpeace was founded in 1971 by a small group of concerned individuals who sailed to the island of Amchitka off the coast of Alaska to try to stop US nuclear weapons testing. To ensure future generations can continue to thrive, Greenpeace works to prevent environmental degradation and support a greener, healthier and more peaceful world. Currently, Greenpeace is a network consisting of 41 local chapters in Europe, America, Asia and the Pacific (Biagini & Sagar, 2004) who work together to carry out environmental campaigns.

Greenpeace is non-partisan and operates independently of corporate or government funding. In turn, ordinary citizens support their efforts, giving them the freedom to fight against environmentally destructive governments and businesses. In addition to lobbying, consumer pressure and public mobilization, Greenpeace investigates and documents the root causes of environmental degradation. In addition to advocating for a greener and more peaceful future, Greenpeace also engages in nonviolent direct action to protect the planet. Greenpeace seeks to dismantle oppressive power structures that have a disproportionate impact on the most vulnerable groups and nature (Greenpeace.usa).

Greenpeace uses many methods in its efforts to save the planet and support environmental sustainability. The goal of this strategy is to engage the public in environmental protection and force policymakers and business leaders to take action.

Table 1: Greenpeace's Strategies for Environmental Advocacy and Action

Independent campaign (non-violent direct action)	To bring attention to environmental problems and put pressure on governments and companies, Greenpeace uses nonviolent direct action. Protests, blockades, and banner removal are examples that fall into this category.
Creative communication	To get people interested in environmental issues, Greenpeace uses innovative communication methods. Using platforms like Facebook and Twitter, creating videos and other forms of media content, and even performing daring stunts all fall into this category.
Lobbying	In terms of environmental policy and legislation, Greenpeace is actively involved in lobbying efforts to influence change. Supporting stricter environmental regulations and opposing actions that harm the environment fall into this category.
Research	Greenpeace's advocacy work is supported by the findings of research it conducts to better understand and address environmental problems. This involves finding out what is causing damage to the planet and finding ways to repair it so that the future can be environmentally friendly and peaceful.
Grassroots organizing	Greenpeace's goal is to create a broad network of activists who care about the environment. This not only means facilitating campaigns and events, but also equipping and educating activists.
Principles of fundraising & Open Donations	As a non-profit organization, Greenpeace is committed to respecting the wishes of its donors and using their contributions to advance a sustainable and peaceful world. By providing aid, supporters can join Greenpeace advocates and activists in their fight for social justice. Anyone in the world can make a tax-deductible donation to Greenpeace to help the organization organize, engage, and take action to combat environmental degradation, climate change, and social injustice. In this way, everyone can help Greenpeace's cause and support the organization's various campaigns and programs.

In this research, the case study highlighted is Munculsloko Village, where Greenpeace opened a donation to help Munculsloko Village which is currently still submerged due to sea water flooding that has risen to the surface. As we know, Timbulsloko Village in Demak Regency, Indonesia, is affected by rising sea levels, coastal erosion and excessive groundwater exploitation. Climate change and the destruction of mangrove swamps to make room for fish farms have transformed the community from an agricultural center into an aquatic world filled with trails and canoes. This settlement is divided into four hamlets: Bogame, Wonorejo, Karanggeneng, and Timbulsloko, with the majority of the population of 3,710 people working as fishermen and factory employees (Mongabay.com, 2021).

Rising sea levels due to climate change are flooding communities and forcing people to flee. Excessive groundwater extraction causes water to sink, aquaculture contributes to the island's worst coastal erosion, and sea levels are rising due to climate change (Japantimes, 2021). Local residents refused to leave their homes and often paid trucks to move soil and stones from hilly areas to protect graves and raise their homes so they would not be submerged in water. To protect Timbulsloko, a pilot project to rebuild previously logged mangrove forests in a number of villages has been undertaken to revitalize and protect at-risk fishing communities and their habitats (Preventionweb, 2022).

One of the factors behind Greenpeace opening donations for the ROB flood case in Timbulsloko is that Greenpeace is directed at increasing public awareness of the impacts of climate change, and this case is an opportunity to involve the community directly in mitigation and recovery efforts.

Greenpeace Indonesia applies donation techniques as a fundamental component in their environmental initiatives. Donations are essential to fund the projects of Greenpeace

Indonesia staff and volunteers, so they can take real action in creating beneficial environmental and social transformation. Greenpeace Indonesia uses funds obtained through donations to support various very significant efforts. This donation primarily provides support for Greenpeace's investigative efforts aimed at documenting environmental violations, uncovering the underlying factors that contribute to these problems, and presenting verifiable information to the general public. Greenpeace uses these funds to produce comprehensive and thorough reports, thereby increasing understanding of the environmental obstacles they face (greenpeace.org).

Additionally, donations empower Greenpeace to implement innovative and impactful campaigns. Campaign teams have the ability to coordinate nonviolent demonstrations, public meetings, and other initiatives aimed at raising public awareness of pressing environmental issues. Donations also help Greenpeace's innovative communications efforts through other channels, such as social media and online platforms, to expand its reach to a wider demographic. Additionally, through financial support from philanthropists, Greenpeace can be actively involved in designing and advocating for laws that uphold environmental conservation. This includes pushing for stricter regulations, formulating laws that support environmental issues, and engaging in discussions with governments and companies to encourage the adoption of sustainable practices.

Greenpeace's privacy policy is specifically designed to protect the personal information of donors, emphasizing the importance of donations. Greenpeace fosters confidence and encourages greater contributions by ensuring the confidentiality and security of donor data. Transparency towards funders is a top priority for Greenpeace Indonesia. Greenpeace sends campaign information to funders, providing regular reports on campaign success, use of funds, and positive results resulting from their contributions.

Greenpeace aims to foster strong and reliable relationships with its donor community, which is why Greenpeace prioritizes transparency.

Greenpeace Indonesia establishes a symbiotic relationship between public funding and real efforts to preserve the environment through this donation technique. Donations function both as a means to provide financial support and as a means for the community to actively participate in environmental conservation and the necessary transformation. In addition, the media also plays an important role in raising public awareness about this case, and Greenpeace wants to take advantage of the media's role in amplifying their message about climate change. Because the impact felt by the people of Timbulsloko Village is real and has a direct impact on the lives of the people there, opening donations is an alternative way to convey to the community that the threat of the climate crisis is real and has an impact on the majority of the community. Even though a campaign has been carried out via social media, "opening donations" is a step that shows the "urgent" pattern of an event, so the implication of this finding is that Greenpeace's efforts to open donations as a response to the ROB flood case in Timbulsloko Village is a relevant strategy and effective in raising awareness about climate change at the local level.

This can be seen from the increase in public participation on one of the social media used by Greenpeace, namely Instagram. Greenpeace's first post regarding open donations on April 15 2023 resulted in 1,181 likes and 12

comments with an impression reach of 37 thousand views. After the first post was made, content related to the ROB flood that occurred in Timbulsloko village experienced a significant increase, where as of June 25 2023, the post about climate change in Tambulsloko village received 5,905 likes and 146 comments and a broadcast reach of 142 thousand views. This shows that the open donation strategy implemented by Greenpeace is able to increase community awareness and sensitivity regarding climate change issues, especially in the village of Munculsloko. It also shows the importance of collaboration with local communities and the ability to respond to the unique challenges faced by a particular community.

The following is an open donation made by Greenpeace as a benchmark to see the extent of community involvement in providing assistance to Munculsloko Village. Currently, there are as many as 250 families whose houses have been flooded due to rising sea levels. This is also exacerbated by the lack of water sources and adequate lighting so that sometimes people only rely on flashlights from cellphones and moonlight when walking at night. Therefore, the installation of solar panels in Timbulsloko is a crowdfunding project from the Greenpeace Indonesia Climate and Energy Campaign to help villagers celebrate Eid al-Fitr with a water and lighting source that meets their needs. Greenpeace opened a fundraising campaign with a target of IDR 109,000,000 according to the funds needed, until May 15 2023.

Table 2: Fundraising Campaign of Greenpeace

Access to clean water for 150 families		
	Work	Funds required
1	Well renovation	Rp. 20,000,000
2	Water pump systems	IDR 28,000,000
3	Solar panel installations in mosques	Rp. 45,000,000
Total		Rp.95,000,000
Street lighting for 200 families		
	Work	Funds required
4	30 pcs solar energy lamps	Rp.9,000,000
6	60 pcs bamboo poles and installation	Rp. 5,000,000
Total		Rp. 14,000,000

From the accumulated donations above, the funds collected were only half of the target that had been set, namely Rp. 49,120,493 from the target of Rp. 109,000,000 million. Even though the target was not achieved, on June 18 2023, a solar-powered water pump was successfully installed and distributed water from the well they had dug since May 31. Not only that, solar-powered village street lighting has also illuminated the village.

There are several aspects to the social conditions of the Timbulsloko village community, such as the level of education, health and income of the community. Regarding the educational level of Timbulsloko village, the average community only reaches high school level so that in their work they can only be fishermen and factory workers, but quite a few people are also unemployed, this is also due to the existing conditions in the Timbulsloko village area which are

inadequate in terms of accessibility. Regarding general health, the people of Timbulsloko village suffer from diabetes, cholesterol and hypertension, because the people consume excessively salty and sweet foods. This is also due to the lack of health facilities such as community health centers/clinics to check the health of the community. The Timbulsloko village community has principles adhered to by its community, namely helping each other to people who are in trouble and cooperation between residents and neighborhood units (RT). Timbulsloko Village has 1 (one) mosque, namely the Nurul Huda Mosque and 4 (four) prayer rooms in each RT which are usually used by the community to carry out several traditions such as recitation of the Koran, charity for orphans and community spirits. Donations for orphans are usually carried out in the month of Suro, while arwah jama' or the community's tradition of praying for their

ancestors is carried out together before the arrival of the month of Ramadan at the Nurul Huda mosque.

In Indonesia itself, success in dealing with climate change also depends on public awareness and participation. However, the level of public interest and involvement is still low. Based on the Indonesian Climate Change Public Opinion Survey conducted by the Indonesia Climate Change Trust Fund (ICCTF) in 2018, only 12% of respondents considered climate change to be the most pressing concern. 57% of Indonesian people, according to the Climate Asia project survey in 2013, are not ready to face the impact of climate change on their country's resources. This shows that there is still little interest and understanding of this problem. Most Indonesians do not fully understand climate change. Therefore, providing them with comprehensive insight into climate change can be a solution to increasing awareness of climate change. Providing education is important because the implementation of government policies aimed at reducing greenhouse gases in Indonesia will be less effective if public awareness of climate change is still low (Pramana & Naini, 2021).

Therefore, Greenpeace, which is a non-governmental organization that has long been active and focused on environmental issues and climate change, continues to make various efforts, starting from campaigns both through social media and directly to opening donations for the community, especially in Indonesia. Through social media, Greenpeace seems to be trying to use technology as a way to attract public attention. Greenpeace views technology as a tool to facilitate the success of its campaigns. Through this context, environmental activists are facilitated by technological devices as a medium to spread their political messages regarding the environmental crisis throughout the world. Greenpeace believes that it can effectively evoke emotional responses through the use of technology in presenting environmental cases (Alam & Nilan, 2018).

Furthermore, Greenpeace Indonesia (2020), believes that community support is the key to the success of campaigns related to commitments to protect climate, sea, air and forests. Community support is also formed in the form of digital activism; namely the role of the community in voicing environmental protection through social media by following the Greenpeace Indonesia account. To date, followers of the Greenpeace Indonesia social media account have reached 1.5 million consisting of (Instagram, Facebook and TikTok) from

community media studying the campaigns, share information, and then take real action.

The first finding from this research is that Greenpeace is opening donations in an effort to overcome the real impact of climate change that is currently occurring in Indonesia. The results of the researchers' analysis show that this organization has identified that community participation in climate change recovery and mitigation efforts is one of the most effective ways to achieve awareness regarding the real impacts of climate change among the community.

The second finding, the motivation of Indonesian people to participate in this donation is driven by factors such as empathy for flood victims, concern for the environment and climate change, and belief in Greenpeace's role as an agent of positive change in environmental issues. In addition, these findings show that Greenpeace's effective communication and outreach, both through traditional media and social media, plays an important role in encouraging community participation. Apart from that, transparency in the use of donated funds also influences participation levels.

Additionally, what is important is pressure from local communities and environmental groups. The Timbulsloko community has long struggled with ROB flooding and the loss of their agricultural land. They have been an important partner for Greenpeace in its efforts to raise awareness about climate change. In situations like these, Greenpeace feels that opening up donations is a tangible way to support the efforts of local communities and respond to their urgent needs.

Community participation in donating has been proven to increase their awareness of the real impacts of climate change. Through donations, the community becomes part of the solution and feels they have a role in overcoming the problems they face. This also allows them to see firsthand how their contribution helps ROB flood victims and the local community. Apart from increasing awareness of climate change, participation in this donation can also increase community involvement in broader environmental issues. When people feel that their efforts are having a positive impact, they tend to be more involved in campaigns and other environmental activities.

On the other hand, cultural factors also play an important role in donating behavior in Indonesia. The following are several cultural factors that influence donating behavior in Indonesia, as researchers summarize below:

Table 3: Cultural Factors that Influence Donating Behavior in Indonesia

Religious beliefs & Trust in institutions	Religion is an important factor in donation behavior in Indonesia, with many people donating to support religious causes or through mosques. Apart from that, trust in institutions such as mosques can influence donation behavior in Indonesia (Kasri & Ramli, 2019)
Helping poor/needy communities	Giving charity to help the poor and needy is also a common motivation for donating behavior in Indonesia (Kasri, 2013)
Seasonal effects	Seasonal effects, such as religious events such as Ramadan, can have a major impact on donor behavior in Indonesia (Zubairi & Siddiqui, 2019).

Distribution preferences	Distribution preferences can also influence donation behavior in Indonesia, where marine resource users in Wakatobi donate money and time based on their preferences (Nelson et al, 2018)
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Overall, cultural elements such as religion, trust in institutions, and seasonal influences all play an important role in donation behavior in Indonesia. Understanding these cultural variables is very important for non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and other organizations looking to raise funds in Indonesia.

III. CONCLUSION

Using the example of the ROB flood in Timbulloko Village, this research highlights the important role of Greenpeace in responding to the negative impacts of climate change in Indonesia. Greenpeace's act of accepting donations appears to be part of a larger campaign to raise public awareness of climate change and inspire more people to take action to combat it. This research shows that people's willingness to donate to Greenpeace in Indonesia is caused by several interrelated things. Greenpeace's reputation as a strong agent of positive change on climate and environmental issues, as well as sympathy for the victims of the recent floods, motivated donors to donate.

Furthermore, this research explores the complex network of cultural influences that shape the attitudes and actions of donors in Indonesia. The report highlights other factors, such as faith in institutions, the impact of seasonal influences, and preferences regarding distribution channels, which are as important as religious beliefs. Understanding these complex cultural aspects is critical to developing an efficient fundraising approach in Indonesia. The importance of community involvement in fighting climate change is an important point in this research. People's sensitivity to environmental problems generally increases when they work together in their communities to address climate change. It is clear that Greenpeace's open contribution strategy is a powerful tool to inspire people to take action and unite behind efforts to combat climate change.

Overall, this research highlights the importance of cooperation between NGOs such as Greenpeace and local communities in combating climate change and improving the state of the environment. Greenpeace's open donation campaign is a powerful model instrument in fighting climate change on a global scale because it raises awareness, inspires engagement, and turns empathy into concrete action. This study emphasizes the importance of NGO and community collaboration, highlighting the shared responsibility to create a sustainable and climate-resilient future.

Because this research is limited to one case study, namely Timbulloko village, it is likely that this research will encounter problems with its generalizability. This means that the results of this research do not necessarily represent other communities or regions in Indonesia or the voices of other NGOs in implementing the same strategy. Apart from that, this research also has limitations because it has not reached Greenpeace and local communities for in-depth interviews so

the data analyzed is only based on literature data. However, what is no less important is the sustainability of this research in the future. This research may seem simple and only focuses on short-term results, namely when Greenpeace campaigns and donations open, but what is most important is how it continues after donations close, and whether people will remain involved after the campaigns and donations are finished.

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- **Tentang Penulis:** Wahyu Wulandari is an alumni of the undergraduate program at Bengkulu University, and is currently pursuing a Master of Political Science degree at the International Islamic University of Indonesia through a scholarship. She presented his work entitled "Greenpeace Indonesia's Open Donation Strategy in Increasing Participation on Climate Change Issues in Timbulsloko Village" at the International Studies Association event in Bangkok, Thailand. If you want to contact her, you can do via email wahyu.wulandari@uiii.ac.id or via her Instagram account, namely @wahyuwulandarii.